

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue II, February 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

**ORAL ENGLISH INSTRUCTION IN SECONDARY VOCATIONAL
EDUCATION IN CHINA: A BLENDED LEARNING APPROACH**

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

GUIQIN QIN, BRENDALYN A. MANZANO

1. Tarlac State University 2. Guangxi Hechi Nationality Agricultural School

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the status of blended learning in Secondary English Teaching in China. It sought to describe the platforms and application software used by teachers and students in blended oral English teaching, how the blended model of teaching carried out by the participants, the problems encountered by the participants while implementing the blended teaching model, and the reform strategies proposed to enhance the secondary vocational oral English instruction.

For the data collection, a questionnaire and interview guide were employed. Four hundred eighty (480) students and 20 teachers participated in the questionnaire survey, while 12 students and 6 teachers participated in the interviews. They were all from two secondary schools in Yizhou District, Hechi City, Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China. The questionnaire was adapted from the AIC-CCS Scale created by Wu et al. (2013). In analyzing the results, mean score, and ranking were used as statistical techniques.

The survey showed that blended learning methods were actively adopted in Chinese secondary vocational schools, which were recognized and preferred by teachers and students to enhance students' oral English competence to a certain extent. The current main teaching platform used was dominated by Superstar Learning, and various interactive oral activities and tasks are arranged on the platform through audio, video, and text. "Fluent English Speaking" was always used by teachers as their learning software while students always used oral learning applications such as Fluent English, English Fun Dubbing and so on. Carrying out the blended teaching model was done in three aspects: preparation, implementation and evaluation.

Teachers often encountered problems in teaching design, communication barriers, integration of teaching resource, technical problems, and teacher training effect. However, teachers sometimes had problems with both time management and evaluation. On the other hand, the problems that students often encountered in oral English learning were lack of real language environment, communication barriers, learning adaptability, and lack of real-time response.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

The results of this study were used as bases in developing the proposed reform strategies for improving oral English teaching in Chinese secondary vocational schools and contributing to the development of English education practice.

Keywords: Oral English Instruction, Secondary Vocational Education in China, A Blended Learning Approach, Blended Teaching Model

Introduction

Blended learning approach combines traditional offline teaching with modern online teaching, blending the advantages of the two new teaching models (Zhang, C., 2023). It provides a rich opportunity and platform for sustainability in education through comprehensive sexuality education, flexibility, resource sharing, teacher professional development and curriculum integration, promoting students' understanding and practice of sustainability and preparing them for future challenges.

However, in China English is a weak subject in most of secondary vocational school, whose students have a strong sense of fear of speaking English, worried about being laughed at, criticized by the teacher, and lost their interest, self-confidence, and motivation to learn English over time. Whether online or offline, students are particularly anxious and nervous in oral expression, have low participation in class, and are reluctant to speak English, leading to the common phenomenon of "dumb English".

In oral English teaching, teachers adopt relatively simple methods, and students are very tired of boring oral English training methods, so the participation is not high, the amount of practice is not enough, and cannot meet the learning needs of students at all levels. Therefore, there is an urgent need to change these situations by adopting an oral English teaching model suitable for secondary vocational school students.

Hence, a new model of instruction, blended learning was developed in the modern era in response to student learning demands and policy requirements. It thoroughly integrates Internet technology into regular classrooms, showcasing its educational value and presenting a novel approach to instruction. This new teaching approach has been widely used in all school sectors in China during the epidemic period, including kindergartens, primary and secondary schools in the compulsory education stage, and colleges and universities. It ensures the learning progress of students, promotes the interaction and communication between teachers and students, and improves the flexibility and adaptability of teaching. Because it

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

combines the significant advantages of online and offline teaching, it has become an important direction of China's education reform. In the post-epidemic era, with the development of education informatization and digitization, blended teaching will become more popular and perfect, and promote education reform and innovation.

Method

A mixed-method approach was used in this study, where the researcher adopted a concurrent design when collecting and analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data during the research process.

The questionnaire survey and interview methods were used to investigate and understand the current situation of oral English teaching in secondary vocational schools and to analyze and study the problems in teaching.

The sample survey used in this study was from two secondary occupation schools in Yizhou District, Hechi City, China. Two hundred fifty (250) participants were randomly collected from each school, including 10 English teachers and 240 students. The student participants came from Grade 1 secondary occupation schools, who had been taught oral English in a blended teaching model. There were 500 participants in total. To verify the implementation of blended oral English teaching, the researchers also conducted semi-structured interviews with some interviewees.

Through the collected data, the researcher analyzed the current situation of blended teaching in secondary vocational English teaching and put forward measures and plans to solve the problem.

The following scale, range, and verbal interpretation were used in analyzing the data.

5	4.50-5.00	Always/Strongly Agree
4	3.50-4.49	Often/Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Sometimes/Neutral
2	1.50-2.49	Rarely/Disagree
1	1.00- 1.49	Never/Strongly Disagree

Results and Discussions

This section illustrates the data gathered in the study, its analyses and the interpretation of the data.

1.1 Use of Teaching Platform

Table 1

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Teachers' Use of Teaching Platform

Items	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Superstar Learning	4.60	Always	1
Secondary Vocational Teaching Resources Network	3.15	Sometimes	2
Wisdom Vocational Education	2.90	Sometim	3
Cloud Classroom	1.70	Rarely	4
Tencent Classroom	1.65	Rarely	5
Chinese University Mooc	1.60	Rarely	6
Type of teaching platform used in school	2.60	Sometimes	
Audio	4.75	Always	1.5
Video	4.75	Always	1.5
Text	4.70	Always	3
Type of teaching resources provided by the teaching platform used in school	4.73	Always	
Total Grand Mean	3.67	Often	

As clearly displayed in Table 1, the total grand mean of 3.67 implies that teachers often use teaching platforms in the English classroom. Specifically, on the item for the "Type of teaching resources provided by the teaching platform used in school", Superstar Learning is the most used platform in secondary schools, with a weighted mean of 4.6 and verbal description as Always, followed by "Wisdom Vocational Education Platform", with a weighted mean of 3.15. The third one is "Wisdom Vocational Education", with a weighted mean of 2.9. And the platforms such as Cloud Classroom, Tencent Classroom and Chinese University Mooc are rarely used by the participants, for their weighted means are all below 1.8. Actually which teaching platform a school would choose depends on whether the platform can provide a variety of teaching tools, such as video recording, online live streaming, homework assignment and correction, etc., whether it is easy to operate with a good sense of user experience, whether it provides stable technical support, and whether it is compatible with a variety of devices and operating systems.

In item "Type of teaching resources provided by the teaching platform used in school show", when teachers are implementing the blended teaching, they utilized

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

various functions and multiple resources such as screen casting, check-in, selection, voting, discussion, audio, video, etc. of the Superstar Learning platform to provide students with more innovative, rich and operational blended classroom teaching in an all-round and multi-dimensional way (Li, H.Y., 2021).

Table 1 clearly shows that after teachers select teaching resources through the teaching platform, they mainly provide them to students in the form of audio, video and text for online and offline learning. The Grand Mean of audio, video and text is 4.70 and the verbal descriptions is Always.

As can be seen from the table, the participants always use the platform of Superstar Learning to release learning tasks to students in the form of audio, video and text for teaching management, select the necessary teaching resources from the platform's resource library for lesson preparation, discuss with students on some learning problems online, and sometimes communicate with parents about students' learning situation through the platform.

Table 2
Students' Use of Teaching/Learning Platform

Items	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Superstar Learning	4.44	Often	1
Secondary Vocational Teaching Resources Network	3.28	Sometimes	2
Wisdom Vocational Education	3.27	Sometimes	3
Cloud classroom	2.24	Rarely	4
Tencent Classroom	2.23	Rarely	5
Chinese University Mooc	2.22	Rarely	6
Teaching platform used in school	2.95	Sometimes	
Online discussion	4.18	Often	1
Sharing learning experiences	4.16	Often	2
Asking questions	4.15	Often	3
Interactive activities through the teaching platforms	4.16	Often	4
Total Grand Mean	3.77	Often	
The use of the teaching platform improves your enthusiasm and initiative in learning English.	4.12	Agree	1
The learning resources (PPT, video,	4.06	Agree	2

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

audio, etc.) provided by the teacher on the teaching platform are of great help to your oral English learning.			
Level of agreement relating to the use of blended teaching platform	4.09	Agree	

The students' use of learning or teaching platform has the total grand mean of 3.77 which implies that students often use them in learning and teaching themselves as well. Notably, the item on "Teaching platform used in school", Superstar Learning was the most used platform in secondary schools, with a weighted mean of 4.44 and a verbal description as Always. The second one is Secondary Vocational Teaching Resources Network, with a weighted mean of 3.28. The third one is Wisdom Vocational Education, with a weighted mean of 3.27. Both items were rated verbally as Sometimes. But the verbal description of these two platforms is below 2.25, so verbal description is Rarely.

The second item "Interactive activities through the teaching platforms" show responds complete the interactive activities designed by teachers through the teaching platform. These interactive activities are Online discussion, with a mean of 4.18, Sharing learning experiences, with a mean of 4.16 and Asking questions, with a mean of 4.15. Their overall grand mean is 4.16, so their verbal description is Often.

In item "Level of agreement relating to the use of blended teaching platform", it can be seen that majority of participants think that using the teaching platform to improve their blended teaching oral learning ability is very helpful. The mean of "The use of the teaching platform improves enthusiasm and initiative in learning English" is 4.12, with a verbal descriptions as Agree. The mean of "The learning resources (PPT, video, audio, etc.) provided by the teacher on the teaching platform are of great help to oral English learning" is 4.06, which is lower than the first item. It was rated verbally as "Agree". In general, the grand mean is 4.09, which shows that the participants Agree to use the current school teaching platform for oral English learning.

Based on the contents of Table 1.1 and Table 1.2, it was shown that the current teaching platform used by secondary vocational schools was dominated by Superstar Learning, and various interactive oral activities were arranged on the platform in the form of audio, video and text. The use of the teaching platform seemed to improve the students enthusiasm and initiative in learning English. Meanwhile the learning resources (PPT, video, audio, etc.) provided by the teacher on the teaching platform are of great help to their oral English learning.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

1.2 Use of Learning Software

Table 3
Teachers' Use of Learning Software

Item	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Fluent English speaking	4.75	Always	1
Interesting English dubbing	4.30	Often	2
Speakg	3.95	Often	3
Coco English	2.30	Rarely	4
Youdao Oral Master	2.05	Rarely	5
VOA Slow English	1.95	Rarely	6
Box fish	1.90	Rarely	7.5
Duolingo	1.90	Rarely	7.5
Kind of oral English teaching software used in school	2.88	Sometimes	
Speech recognition and correction	4.55	Always	1.5
Speaking exercises	4.55	Always	1.5
Learning database	4.10	Often	2
Interactive exercises and games	4.00	Often	2
Software functions used to design oral teaching activities	4.30	Often	
Before class	4.70	Always	1
After class	4.65	Always	2
During class	4.60	Always	3
Usage of the learning software in the teaching-learning process	4.65	Always	
Total Grand Mean	3.94	Often	

The item "Software functions used to design oral teaching activities" shows what functions of learning software teachers often use when designing oral English teaching activities. The grand mean is 4.32, with a verbal description as Often. In these Software functions, speech recognition and correction as well as speaking exercises were Always designed in oral English teaching activities, with the same mean of 4.70. Likewise, the mean of learning database is 4.10, while the mean of interactive

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

exercises and games is 4.00. These two kinds of software were Often used in designing oral English teaching activities.

In the item "Usage of the learning software in the teaching-learning process", it shows that the use of the learning software before class, during class, and after class received the grand mean 4.65 with the mean 4.70, 4.65, and 4.60, respectively. This means that the learning software is always used in these three parts of the teaching-learning process.

Due to the different functions and features of each learning software, teachers choose different teaching software according to the teaching objectives, and design teaching tasks and activities for students according to the learning situation and teaching objectives, and evaluate and give feedback on the learning effect of students through the evaluation function of the software.

Table 4
Students' Use of Learning Software

Items	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Use oral learning apps (such as Fluent English, Duolingo, Box fish, English Fun Dubbing) to learn	4.51	Always	1
Have conversations with others in English	4.23	Often	2
Listen to English songs and watch English movies	4.20	Often	3
English Speech Contest	3.74	Often	4
Oral English class by foreign teachers	2.41	Rarely	5
Ways to improve oral English	3.82	Often	
Language environment	4.11	Often	1
Plenty of oral practice opportunities	4.10	Often	2
Authentic oral English expressions	4.08	Often	3
Assistant provided by oral English learning software	4.10	Often	
Self-directed learning	4.04	Often	1
Self-evaluation	3.99	Often	2
Online discussion and interaction	3.97	Often	3
Activities employed using the oral English software	4.00	Often	
Total Grand Mean	3.97	Often	

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

The total grand mean 3.97 for the students' use of learning software indicates that students often use the learning software. It implies further that since students are highly literate in technology, they can navigate different learning software as often as they can for them to address their learning needs.

In item "Ways to improve oral English", participants used various ways for their oral English language improvement. Of the six ways in the table, using oral learning apps (such as Fluent English, Duolingo, Box fish, English Fun Dubbing) to learn English got the highest mean 4.51 with a verbal description of Always. This means that among the many English learning methods, students were more willing to use English software to assist them in learning. Next is having conversations with others in English, which got the mean of 4.23. Third is listening to English songs and watching English movies, with a mean of 4.20. Fourth in rank is participating in an English Speech Contest, with a mean of 3.74. The last three items just mentioned got the same verbal description of Often. Lastly, having oral English classes by foreign teachers had a mean of 2.41, with a verbal description of Rarely. Due to financial and talent reasons, these two secondary vocational schools had few opportunities to hire foreign teachers to take oral English classes. The Grand mean of these six ways is 3.95, with a verbal description of Often. This means that the participants Often used the above learning ways, except oral English classes by foreign teachers.

As for item "Assistant provided by oral English learning software", when the participants learn oral English learning software, it creates good learning conditions for English learning, such as language environment, plenty of oral practice opportunities, and authentic oral English expressions. Their means are 4.11, 4.10 and 4.08 respectively and their grand mean is 4.10, with a verbal description of Often.

Item "Activities employed using the oral English software" presents what activities the participants mainly do when they use the oral English software. In these activities, the mean of Self-directed learning is 4.04, the mean of self-evaluation is 3.99 and the mean of online discussion and interaction is 3.97. All these activities were often employed using the oral English software in learning English. It shows that oral English software can cultivate students' consciousness and autonomy in learning English.

Based on Tables 3 and 4, oral English learning software is an essential assistant in students' English learning and a major component of blended teaching, which is very popular with students. The learning software provides good Language environment plenty of oral practice opportunities and authentic oral English expressions. Students conduct self-directed learning, self-evaluation and online discussion and interaction through the use of oral English software. By the functions of

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

the intelligent evaluation in the oral English software students can find the shortcomings in their learning and correct their mistakes in time. In addition, extracurricular resources through learning software can also expand students' knowledge and vision, improve their interest in English learning and independent learning ability.

2. Carrying out the Blended Teaching Model

2.1 Preparation

Table 5
Teachers' Preparation

Items	Mean	Verbal Description
Developing lesson plans	4.60	Always
Selecting teaching platforms and software	4.50	Always
Integration of online and offline teaching resources	4.50	Always
Conducting instructional design	4.45	Often
Training and instructing students	4.40	Often
Developing teaching strategies	3.98	Often
Developing evaluation criteria	3.65	Often
Preparation for blended teaching	4.28	Often
Teaching PPT	4.23	Often
Teaching videos	3.92	Often
Teaching cases	3.74	Often
Interactive games	3.66	Often
Micro-lessons	3.40	sometimes
Online and offline teaching resources prepared	3.79	Often
My school has the technical support and guarantee required for blended teaching.	4.60	Strongly Agree
I can cope with and solve problems IT capacity in technical support.	3.90	Agree
Level of agreement relating to blended teaching preparation	4.25	Agree
Total Grand Mean	4.11	Often

Teachers' preparation garnered a total grand mean of 4.11 which indicates that teachers often prepare for blended teaching and their teaching resources. "Preparation for blended teaching", got the mean of 4.41, with an overall verbal

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

description as Often. In these ways, such as developing lesson plans (M= 4.60), selecting teaching platforms and software (M=4.50), integration of online and offline teaching resources (M=4.50), conducting instructional design (M=4.45), training and instructing students (M4.00), developing teaching strategies (M=3.98) and developing evaluation criteria (M=3.65) are Often used by the participants in preparation for blended teaching.

In the preparation of blended teaching, the first task to do is to develop lesson plans, then choose the appropriate teaching platform and software, and then integrate online and offline teaching resources according to the teaching content. The most difficult part in this preparation is the integration of teaching resources, which requires teachers to have certain informatization teaching ability and master the teaching content skillfully. They also need to use innovative thinking and imagination to skillfully combine various teaching resources to form creative teaching design. To carry out blended teaching, teaching strategies should be formulated according to the actual situation of students, so that students can learn effectively under the guidance of the method. Finally the evaluation criteria for online and offline learning is not something a single teacher can do, and it needs to be completed by a team at the beginning of each semester.

In item "online and offline teaching resources prepared", we can see what kind of preparation teachers have made with these resources. The grand mean is 3.79, with a verbal description as Often. Teaching using PPT and videos, with the mean of 4.23 and 3.92 respectively, are the most common teaching methods in current information-based teaching and require teacher preparation. In order to make the teaching content more specific and vivid, It is also necessary to prepare some teaching cases (M=3.74) . English classes emphasize interaction between teachers and students or between students, so teachers need to prepare some interactive games in advance to enhance the atmosphere and interest of the class (M=3.66). In addition, since most of the blended teaching adopts flipped classroom, therefore, it is necessary to prepare to make some micro-lessons (M=3.40) or find relevant micro-lesson videos in the resource library for students to review before class and preview after class. Because it is not always possible to find suitable micro-lessons and they are difficult to make, its mean is slightly lower than others, but in general, these methods are often used by teachers when preparing for teaching.

The last item of this dimension is about "Level of agreement relating to blended teaching preparation." As shown in this item, the grand mean is 4.25, with an overall verbal description as Agree. Most of the participants Strongly Agree (M=4.60) that their school had the technical support and guarantee required for blended

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

teaching, with a mean of Strong Agree. Because the basic construction of information-based teaching in China's secondary vocational schools has been very complete, it is fully equipped with the hardware conditions needed for blended teaching. The second is about teachers' informatization teaching ability, with an average score of 3.90, with the verbal description as Agree. After all, there are differences in teachers' ability of information-based teaching. Some older teachers lack this ability, while young teachers have been trained in information-based teaching since college, so that they can cope with and solve problems IT capacity in technical support.

Based on Table 3.1, participants show that the schools have provided teaching hardware support for blended teaching, and the teachers have acquired certain information teaching ability through teaching training, and are able to carry out teaching design for the combination of online and offline modes of teaching. In short, the participants have made preparations for blended teaching.

Table 6
Students' Preparation

Items	Mean	Verbal Description
Have the hardware devices and know how to use them	4.00	Often
Understand learning resources	3.85	Often
Arrange time reasonably	3.42	Sometimes
Keep a positive attitude	3.30	Sometimes
Have good study habits	2.80	Sometimes
Preparation for blended learning	3.47	Sometimes
Grand Mean		

As displayed in item "Preparation for blended learning", the grand mean of this dimension is 3.47, with an overall verbal description as Sometimes. It shows that most participants were Sometimes prepared for blended learning. They had the hardware for blended learning and know how to use it ($M=4.00$), which shows that the student's ability to apply and understand the software is relatively better, with a verbal description as Often. As for understanding the content of learning resources, its mean is 3.85, which means that students can often understand the content of learning resources. However, the mean is not too high for the three areas because the students Sometimes did arranging time reasonably ($M= 3.42$), keeping a positive attitude

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

(M=3.30), and having good study habits (M=2.80). This happened because some secondary vocational students did not have good study habits; their study consciousness and initiative were not strong, and often needed the supervision of the teachers to complete their requirements. They could not rationalize their study time and maintain a positive attitude towards learning for a long time.

Tables 5 and 6 showed that most teachers did a good job of preparing for the blended teaching. But the preparation of students still needs to be strengthened, especially from the students' ideological education, to cultivate students' good learning habits and active and serious attitude towards learning. These are prerequisites to ensure effectiveness of using blended learning.

2.2 Implementation

Item "Implementation measures of the blended teaching model" presents how the participants implement the blended teaching model. The grand mean of these measures is 3.71, with a verbal description as Often. The means of the first two measures are 4.60 and 4.55 respectively, which means that teachers always take these measure to implement blended teaching. Teaching using online platforms and flipped classroom got the weighted mean 3.85 and 3.65 respectively, which indicates that teachers often use these measures. But the mean of the last two measures are 3.35 and 2.61 respectively, which indicates that teachers Sometimes take these measures. It shows that the online evaluation and feedback should be more timely, and the cultivation of students' cross-cultural awareness should also be strengthened. When these measures are strongly promoted and implemented, blended learning can run smoothly.

Table 7
Teachers' Implementation

Items	Mean	Verbal Description
Conducting classroom speaking activities	4.60	Always
Designing blended instruction	4.55	Always
Combining online and offline instruction	3.96	Often
Teaching with online platforms	3.85	Often
Flipped classroom	3.65	Often
Online evaluation, feedback and improvement	3.35	Sometimes
Fostering intercultural awareness	2.61	Sometimes
Implementation measures of the blended teaching model	3.71	Often

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Pre-lesson preview	4.60	Always
Post-lesson review	4.60	Always
Face-to-face guidance and communication	4.50	Always
Extended learning	4.05	Often
Usage of online platform to combine with online and offline teaching	4.43	Often
Talking about topics	4.30	Often
Role-playing	4.10	Often
Dubbing contest	3.85	Often
Ways on designing speaking practice activities online	4.08	Often
Cooperative group talk	4.40	Often
Role-playing	4.20	Often
Simulated scenes	3.63	Often
Subject debate	2.80	Sometimes
English corner	2.47	Rarely
Ways on designing speaking practice activities offline	3.50	Sometime
Total Grand Mean	3.93	Often

Table 7 presents "Teachers' Implementation" of blended teaching which garnered the total grand mean of 3.93 which means that teachers often observed or implemented blended teaching in the secondary vocational school context in China.

How to use online platform to effectively combine online and offline teaching is a difficult point of blended teaching. As can be seen from the item "Usage of online platform to combine with online and offline teaching", participants mainly use the teaching platform to do pre-lesson preview, post-lesson review, extended learning and face-to-face guidance and communication. Among all the descriptions, the means of the first three are 4.60, 4.60 and 4.50, with the verbal description as Always. However, the last mean score 4.05 for extended learning means an often use of the online platform to combine with offline platform or blended teaching. This is slightly lower than the previous ones because teachers sometimes do not control the time well in the course of teaching and slightly ignore the part of extended learning. Hence, the grand mean of the factor is 4.43, with a verbal description as Often., which means that extended learning affected the overall use of blended teaching.

Blended teaching combines online teaching with offline teaching, and online

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

teaching is an important part of it. Like oral teaching, communication and interaction are essential. Oral activities designed by teachers are very helpful to improve students' oral ability training. The item "Ways on designing speaking practice activities online" shows how participants design effective oral practice activities online. In these activities, talking about topics has the highest mean (4.30), Role-playing ranks second (M=4.10), dubbing contest ranks third (M=3.85), the grand mean of the factors is 4.08, with a verbal description as often. In other words, these three kinds of oral activities are often used by teachers when designing online oral activities. Because the dubbing contest is relatively difficult, the score is slightly lower than the previous two activities.

Similarly, offline face-to-face teaching is also an important part of blended teaching. There are many offline oral teaching activities in secondary vocational schools. The following five activities are ranked in order: Cooperative group talk (M=4.40), role-playing (M=4.20), simulated scenes, (M=3.63), subject debate (M=2.8), English corner (M=2.47). The grand mean of these activities is 3.50, with a verbal description as Often. The means of cooperative group talk, role-playing and simulated scenes is above 3.50, indicating that these two activities are Often used by teachers, after all, they are easier to operate and students are more willing to participate in. However the mean of subject debate is 2.80, and its verbal description is Sometimes. This activity is required for students' to acquire better English skills, for example, students must have a certain knowledge reserve and good oral English expression ability to participate in this activity, but after all, for secondary vocational students only a small group has so good ability, so teachers only sometimes use this activity to teach oral English. The last activity is the English Corner (M=2.47), which has a low mean and its verbal description is Rarely. Since the English Corner is a small club activity, it requires a group of students who love oral English to form a group and have some oral practice activities in the club every week. However, as the students' enthusiasm for organizing an English Corner is low, the club rarely carries out activities.

Table 8
Students' Implementation

Items	Mean	Verbal Description
Group discussion	3.97	Often
Role play	3.94	Often
Simulation scenes	3.87	Often
Film dubbing	3.32	Sometimes
Subject debate	2.75	Sometimes

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

English corner	2.40	Rarely
Activities employed in blended oral learning	3.38	Sometimes
I prefer to interact with classmates online about oral topics.	3.97	Agree
I like group cooperative learning for oral training.	3.95	Agree
I prefer offline oral communication and interaction with classmates on oral topics.	3.53	Agree
Level of agreement relating to blended learning implementation	3.95	Agree

In blended oral learning, teachers arrange some online and offline activities for students to train before, during, and after class. From the Item "Activities employed in blended oral learning", the grand mean is 3.38, with a verbal description as Sometimes. In these activities, group discussion, role play, simulation scenes are the learning activities often adopted by students. The means of these activities are 3.97, 3.94, and 3.87 respectively. Comparatively speaking, these three activities are not very difficult and are easy for students to conduct. While film dubbing and attention debate are very interesting, they require students to have better oral ability, strong imitation ability, and courage. Not many students can meet this requirement, so their mean is not high, with 3.32 and 2.75 respectively, which shows that students Sometimes participate in these two activities, and their participation depends on the difficulty of the activity, theme, or content given by the teacher. The last activity is English corner, with a mean of 2.40, which is the most difficult activity. Due to the students' English foundation, few students participate in this activity and it is not popular among students. For this factor, the second question in the student interview, Speaker 2 and Speaker 5 both have the same opinion.

The item "Level of agreement relating to blended learning implementation" reveals students' acceptance of blended learning implementation in schools. The grand mean of the factor is 3.95, with a verbal description as Agree, which indicates that the mean values of students who like to participate in online oral activities and offline oral activities are 3.97 and 3.53 respectively, indicating that more students like online oral activities, because online oral communication is man-machine and students feel more relaxed. While offline oral activities should be for teachers and classmates, some students with poor English or introverted students were ashamed to express their views in English for fear of making mistakes. For this factor, the third question in the student interview, Speaker 5 and Speaker 11 both have the same

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

opinion.

In these oral activities, students also prefer group cooperative learning for oral training, with a mean of 3.95. Because the strength of a group is greater than that of an individual, it is easier for group members to cooperate with each other than to complete the task alone, and they also make progress through mutual help.

Based on Table 8, students are very supportive of implementing blended learning. However, in the choice of learning activities, they tend to be more difficult, although some activities and tasks are more interesting, but for students with weak English foundation can only be discouraged. Therefore, teachers should be more personalized when designing teaching activities. Students can choose their favorite learning activities according to their learning ability, and they can happily complete the oral tasks assigned by teachers and achieve the expected teaching goals.

Table 8 shows that many teachers take active and effective measures in blended oral English teaching. Through the rich teaching resources and content provided by the teaching platform, the online and offline teaching activities are designed to run through all aspects of the blended teaching. At the same time, some students have a positive attitude towards the implementation of blended oral English teaching and are willing to participate in and cooperate with their favorite oral English activities.

2.3 Evaluation

Table 9
Teachers' Evaluation

Items	Mean	Verbal Description
Pronunciation, intonation and fluency	4.65	Always
Vocabulary and sentence pattern	4.55	Always
Communication strategy	4.35	Often
Grammar	4.20	Often
The content of language knowledge and skill module evaluation	4.63	Always
Daily performance	4.54	Always
Class participation	4.50	Always
Work and project completion	4.50	Always
Self-evaluation and reflection	3.82	Often
Peer response	3.15	Sometimes
The bases of formative evaluation	4.10	Often
Final exam score	4.60	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Comprehensive performance evaluation	4.55	Always
Teacher's concluding comments	4.50	Always
Portfolio evaluation	2.72	Sometimes
Parent feedback	1.66	Rarely
The bases of summative evaluation	3.61	Often
Total Grand Mean	4.11	Often
The combination of formative and summative evaluation can more accurately reflects students' language proficiency.	4.20	Agree
My current use of evaluation criteria can objectively and comprehensively reflect the actual situation of students.	4.00	Agree
I can give timely online and offline evaluation and feedback to students.	3.47	Neutral
Level of agreement relating to blended teaching evaluation	3.89	Agree

The total grand mean on teachers' evaluation is 4.11, which means teachers Often evaluate students' language knowledge and skill. "The content of language knowledge and skill module evaluation" presents what the contents of language knowledge and skills module evaluation of spoken English are. The mean of pronunciation, intonation and fluency is 4.56 while vocabulary and sentence pattern is 4.35, both with verbal description as Often. Communication strategy and grammar, on the hand, has the mean of 4.35 and 4.20 respectively, with both verbal descriptions as Often. The grand mean of this factor is 4.63, which shows that most teachers Always evaluate students' oral English in the second language classroom.

The item on "The basis of formative evaluation" presents what the basis of formative evaluation are, which scores grand mean of 4.10, with a verbal description as Often. The mean of Students Daily performance , Class participation and Work and project completion is 4.54 , 4.50 and 4.50 respectively, which shows that participants always make formative evaluations of students according to these three evaluation contents. Self-evaluation and reflection scores the weight mean of 3.82, with a verbal description as Often . And the mean of peer response is 3.15. And teachers only use this form of evaluation Sometimes. In fact, students' self-evaluation and mutual evaluation are very good evaluate methods, but some students fail to evaluate themselves and their peers objectively, and and the feedback on their own learning

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

is also coped with in passing. The evaluation results are too different from the facts, resulting in many teachers' evaluation in these two aspects will be intercepted, especially in peer response, teachers only sometimes use this kind of evaluation.

Further, on "The basis of summative evaluation", the grand mean is 3.61, with a verbal description as Often. It shows that among the first three bases, summative evaluation was preferred by teachers, so the mean is above 4.50 and the verbal description is Always. But the mean of portfolio evaluation is 2.72, which shows that teachers Sometimes use this form of evaluation because some students are required to write all their works into a booklet for evaluation, after all, it is more time- and energy-consuming. In all these bases, parents' feedback score is the lowest, mainly because there is not much contact between teachers and parents, moreover parents have different cultural qualities, their language evaluation of children is very subjective, few teachers would take it as the basis for evaluation.

Likewise, the level of agreement relating to blended teaching evaluation received the mean 3.89, which means that teachers Agree on their current evaluation practices. The combination of formative and summative evaluations and the current use of evaluation criteria got the means 4.20 and 4.00 respectively and both have a verbal description as Agree. It shows that most of the teachers think that these are effective. The mean of giving online and offline evaluations and feedback to students is 3.47, which indicates that teachers are Neutral in giving timely evaluation and feedback to students. As the evaluation involves both online and offline, it will certainly cost teachers more time and energy, so sometimes there will be a phenomenon of delayed evaluation.

In a word, the methods and bases of formative and terminal evaluation adopted by teachers are more scientific and suitable for students, which are well recognized and supported by most teachers.

Meanwhile, Table 10 presents the mean and verbal description of "Students' Evaluation". The total grand mean of forms of language evaluation and aspects of oral ability is 4.01, which means that students are Often informed about the aspects and forms of evaluation. The "Aspects of oral ability evaluated" shows that participants are evaluated in six aspects of language proficiency. From the table, we can see the grand mean which is 4.02, with a verbal description as Often. These six aspects were arranged as follows: Interaction ability (M=4.05), Learning attitude (M=4.04), Intonation (M=4.02), Fluency and coherence (M=4.01), Oral expression (M=4.00), and Cooperation ability (M=3.98). Their verbal descriptions are all "Often". It shows that most students can clearly understand the content of language evaluation.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Table 10
Students' Evaluation

Items	Mean	Verbal Description
Interaction ability	4.05	Often
Learning attitude	4.04	Often
Intonation	4.02	Often
Fluency and coherence	4.01	Often
Oral expression	4.00	Often
Cooperation ability	3.98	Often
Aspects of oral ability evaluated	4.02	Often
Formative evaluation record sheet	4.01	Often
Descriptive language evaluation	4.01	Often
Quantitative evaluation form for classroom activities	3.99	Often
English oral test scoring sheet	3.99	Often
Forms of language evaluation	4.00	Often
Total Grand Mean	4.01	Often
I am satisfied that my school uses a combination of formative and summative evaluation to evaluate oral English proficiency.	4.00	Agree
The current evaluation standards adopted by the teacher can objectively and comprehensively evaluate the actual situation of my oral English.	3.98	Agree
I can humbly accept my teacher's evaluation and feedback and correct my shortcomings in time.	3.46	Neutral
My teacher can give timely online and offline evaluation and feedback to students.	3.28	Neutral
Level of agreement relating to blended teaching evaluation	3.68	Agree

For forms of language evaluation, from the item "Forms of oral evaluation", it shows that four kinds of evaluation Often appear in language evaluation. These are formative evaluation record and descriptive language evaluation, both have the mean of $M=4.01$; on the other hand, quantitative evaluation form for classroom activities and English oral test scoring sheet have both a mean of 3.99. Their grand mean is 4.00, with a verbal description as Often. It shows that most students can clearly understand the forms of language evaluation.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

As for "Level of agreement relating to blended teaching evaluation", the grand mean of this factor is 3.68, with a verbal description as Agree. Their satisfaction on the formative and summative evaluations as well as their objective evaluation of the current evaluation standards have the means 4.00 and 3.98 respectively, which means that the students Agree with the current evaluation methods. The means of their acceptance and support on the timely evaluation of teachers are 3.46 and 3.28 respectively, with both verbal description as Neutral. It indicates that only some students can humbly accept their teacher's evaluation and feedback and correct their shortcomings in time. It is mainly because many secondary students are not serious about their own learning attitude, are not autonomous, are a little lazy, and have not established better learning habits. As for the teacher, sometimes they can not give timely online and offline evaluation and feedback to students. Because the evaluation method is more complicated, it will certainly cost teachers more time and energy, resulting in the phenomenon of feedback delay. These were supported by Speaker 3 and Speaker 10 during the interview.

From Table 10, it shows that most students know about the aspects of oral ability evaluated by the teacher and the evaluation methods currently used in schools. Overall, they were satisfied with the way they were evaluated.

Based on Tables 9 and Table 10, it is conclusive that the evaluation methods now used at the secondary level are reasonable, satisfactory, and recognized by most of the teachers and students.

3.Problems Encountered in Blended Oral English Teaching and Learning

3.1 Teacher-Related Aspects .

Table 11

Teacher-Related Aspects

Items	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Teaching design	4.05	Often	1
Student participation	4.00	Often	2
Integration of teaching resources	3.75	Often	3
Technical problems	3.60	Often	4
Teacher training effect	3.52	Often	5
Time management	3.23	sometimes	6
Evaluation methods	3.12	Sometimes	7
Grand Mean	3.61	Often	

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

As presented in Table 11, the grand mean of “Teachers-Related Aspect” is 3.61, which shows that participants Often have problems in blended oral English teaching. Among these problems, teaching design has the highest mean, which is 4.05. It shows that teachers still have some problems in how to design the online and offline courses. For example, the teaching content is too boring, the teaching methods are unchanging, and the teaching activities are monotonous, making it difficult to stimulate students' interest in learning.

The problem of student participation is also very troublesome to teachers because many secondary vocational students have not formed good learning habits in the middle school stage, poor English learning foundation, do not listen carefully in class, and are unwilling to participate in various learning activities, and some teachers focus on the explanation of language knowledge, lack of oral practice, resulting in these students unwilling to speak English. Therefore, the mean of this problem is 4.00, with the verbal description as Often.

Because of the varieties of teaching resources on the current teaching platform and software, for teachers, according to the teaching content, the integration of online and offline teaching resources, effective integration of the two teaching advantages, is a thorny problem faced by some teachers. The mean of this problem is 3.75, with the verbal description as Often. In the process of resource integration, problems such as low matching degree of resources, low quality of resources, untimely update, imperfect sharing function, lack of necessary technology application ability of some teachers, improper teaching strategies, etc., may lead to poor integration and use of resources.

The problem of teacher training effect ($M=3.52$) Often troubles teachers. Because some teachers lack the corresponding technical ability and teaching strategy technical ability required by blended teaching, they encounter difficulties in implementing blended teaching. For some teachers, most of the teacher training only adopts the traditional face-to-face teaching method, and the lack of personalized learning experience and practical opportunities makes the training effect is not good. Moreover, the content of some training courses is too theoretical and disconnected from the actual teaching scenes of teachers, resulting in teachers being unable to apply something they have learned to practice. Some teachers have low participation in training due to the conflict of work arrangements.

In terms of time management, the mean of it is 3.23, with the verbal description as Sometimes. There are two aspects of the problem. The first one is time allocation. Blended teaching requires teachers to teach in both classroom and online environments, which may require more time to prepare and conduct. The second one

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

is time conflict. In blended teaching, teachers may need to deal with online and face-to-face teaching activities at the same time, which may lead to time conflict. It is a challenge to arrange the time to ensure that both teaching activities can be carried out effectively.

As for Evaluation methods ($M=3.12$), at present, many secondary vocational schools have developed some evaluation systems, but some teachers Sometimes have some problems in teaching. It mainly appears in two aspects. The first aspect is evaluation difficulties. Blended teaching may require teachers to evaluate students' performance in both online and face-to-face environments, which may increase the difficulty of evaluation. Second, the feedback is not timely: for online learning students, teachers may not be able to give timely feedback, which may affect the learning effect of students.

Based on their responses, teachers often or sometimes have problems in all teacher-related aspects. This requires teachers to actively participate in teacher training, master information teaching methods, resource integration methods, and carefully carry out online and online teaching design according to the individual needs of students. Psychological counseling of students, enhancing students' interest in learning, improving their participation, optimizing the formative evaluation and final evaluation system, rationally arranging the online and offline teaching time, and timely evaluating and giving feedback to students' learning are some measures to optimize the use of blended teaching.

3.2 Student-Related Aspects

Table 12
Student-Related Aspects

Items	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Lack of real language environment	4.06	Often	1
Communication barriers	3.92	Often	2
Learning adaptability	3.92	Often	3
Lack of real-time response	3.79	Often	4
The learning effect	3.63	Often	5
Difficult to stick to	3.59	Often	6
Lack of necessary equipment or technical support	2.32	Rarely	7
Grand Mean	3.60	Often	

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Table 12 shows the problems encountered by students in implementing blended learning. The grand mean of the factor is 3.72, with a verbal description as Often. The "lack of real language environment", which ranks first, has the mean 4.06 and a verbal description as Often. For online platforms and software, teachers require designated learning videos and audio recordings for students to watch and practice oral English. However, some teachers pay more attention to the teaching of language knowledge, rather than taking into account the actual language use environment, ignoring the introduction of cultural background, and insufficient interactive communication in oral English, resulting in a lack of real context for many students.

Next is on "communication barriers" with the mean of 3.92 and a verbal description as Often. Students' communication barriers mainly come from their lack of confidence in learning English, coupled with the fact that English is their weakness, lack of basic language knowledge of English, and insufficient skill in listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Meanwhile "learning adaptability" has the mean of 3.92 and verbal description as Often. When students enter secondary vocational schools, most of them switch from traditional offline teaching to online blended learning, and they can not get used to this new teaching methods right away.

Whether online or offline teaching, students all hope that teachers can evaluate and give feedback on their learning effect in time. However, due to the heavy workload of teachers, sometimes it is inevitable to delay, so there is a "lack of real-time response ($M=3.79$).

It is also one of the problems that students Often occur in blended learning. "The learning effect is not significant" ($M=3.63$), with a verbal description as Often. As we know, the good or bad learning effect is not only related to the teacher's teaching ability and the student's own learning ability, but also related to the learning environment, learning motivation and learning methods and strategies. If the learning effect is not significant, it is necessary to find the reasons from the above aspects.

Some students often think that English learning is "difficult to stick to" ($M=3.59$). Since English is their weakness, teachers should not only carry out ideological education and psychological guidance to students, but to help students overcome their weakness, guide them to face their difficulties, and adjust their teaching styles according to students' levels. In the teaching process, it is necessary to develop personalized learning plans according to students' learning conditions and teach according to students' talents. Only in this way can teachers encourage students to persist in learning English. The last statement is "lack of necessary equipment or technical support". Its mean is 2.32, with a verbal description as Rarely. Because

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHUM

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

blended oral English teaching often involves both online and face-to-face communication, the stability and reliability of technology is essential for a hassle-free teaching. However, in actual teaching, there are occasional technical problems, such as unstable network connections, poor audio or video transmission quality, and online platform crashes. These may affect the learning experience of students and the teaching effectiveness of teachers, but such cases rarely occur in the two schools surveyed. Because their hardware facilities fully met the requirements of blended teaching, wireless network covers the whole school, and every student has the mobile devices needed for network teaching.

As shown in Table 12, the problems that students often encounter in oral English learning are as follows: lack of real language environment, communication barriers, learning adaptability, lack of real-time response, and learning effect and difficulty to stick to. However, the lack of necessary equipment or technical support was rarely a problem.

4. Proposed English Instruction Reform Strategies

Just as agreed by all interviewees upon question 1, the blended teaching-learning helps improve the oral English ability of secondary vocational students.

According to the results and findings of the evaluation of description of the blended model in terms of use of platform and software, most teachers and students can understand the characteristics of the platform and software, and can often use the teaching platform and software to teach and learn. In the preparation, implementation, and evaluation of carrying out the blended model, most teachers and students can realize the work content of the three stages, and can often complete the tasks of the three stages. Moreover, most teachers and students have a positive attitude towards blended learning. As regards problems encountered by the participants in the process of blended oral English learning, teachers and students often have some problems in different aspects. This indicates that there is a need for Chinese secondary vocational school to conduct reform strategies to enhance oral English instruction by blended learning.

Hence, recommendations on blended oral English teaching in secondary vocational schools can be obtained from the interviewees. These recommendations are summarized as follows:

4.1. Teachers' Aspect: In order to teach with information technology, teachers need to be proficient in the use of teaching platforms and software as well as the selection of online teaching resources, teachers should actively participate in

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

information-based teaching training, or participate in English subject information-based teaching competitions to promote competition and improve the ability to use information technology. They should select and integrate the resources according to teaching needs and do a good job in information-based teaching design and rationally arrange online and offline teaching activities. Likewise, they should create a comprehensive evaluation system, formulate evaluation standards for online and offline oral evaluation, and improve the objectivity, science and rationality of comprehensive evaluation, strengthen students' ideological guidance and education, analyze students' problems, formulate strategies, change teaching methods, strengthen students' psychological guidance, and improve the evaluation system so that students can enhance their oral English communicative .

4.2 Students' Aspect: Students should have a certain degree of technology application ability, learn to use the school's learning platform and software. Students should also have good self-management ability, clear their own learning goals, reasonable arrangement of time, master the learning progress, and adjust the learning plan according to the actual situation. At the same time, students also need to learn self-evaluation, timely find and improve their shortcomings. Besides, students should pay attention to the ability of independent learning and exploration, actively participate in the learning process, take the initiative to find and solve problems, and constantly improve their learning ability and quality. Meanwhile students need to have good collaborative learning ability and improve the ability of oral English communication in group activities. Further, students also need to have the ability to adapt to change, to embrace change with a positive attitude, and learn to adapt to new environments and learning styles.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

1.The current main teaching platform used by secondary vocational schools is dominated by Superstar Learning, and various interactive oral activities and tasks are arranged on the platform in the form of audio, video, and text. The learning software provides plenty of learning recourse to improve students' interest in English learning and for independent learning ability. The powerful functions of the teaching platform and software give great help to students' oral English learning in the three links of teaching.

2. Carrying out the blended teaching model is mainly reflected in three aspects: preparation, implementation, and evaluation. After teachers selected teaching resources through the teaching platform, they mainly provided them to students in the

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

form of audio, video, and text for online and offline learning, and carry out communication activities between teachers and students. Teachers also arranged group collaborative learning and discussion and provided targeted and personalized guidance to students. Likewise, students complete the practical training and classroom performance of feedback evaluation and the whole classroom learning to answer and simplify questions. Moreover, at this stage, formative evaluation runs through the whole teaching process.

3. The problems that students often encounter in oral English learning are as follows: lack of real language environment, communication barriers, learning adaptability, lack of real-time response, and lack of confidence. But lack of necessary equipment or technical support is rarely a problem. While teachers often have problems in teaching design, communication barriers, integration of teaching resources, technical problems, teacher training effect. However, teachers sometimes have problems with both time management and evaluation. All these problems should be solved one by one to adapt to the development of blended teaching.

Based on the conclusions, the recommendations are presented as follows.

1. School administrators should first provide a variety of hardware and software equipment needed for blended teaching, and provide a stable and user-friendly network course management system. Secondly, they should arrange special system maintenance personnel, responsible for system update, maintenance, as well as management and analysis of data. Thirdly, they ought to arrange special educational staff to supervise the teaching process and ensure that teachers teach according to the teaching plan. Lastly, they should develop scientific evaluation standards, including the evaluation of students' learning effect and the evaluation of teachers' teaching quality.

2. Experts from within and outside the school should be arranged to carry out relevant teaching lectures and special teaching training, and support. They should encourage teachers to participate in teaching ability competitions of various disciplines to promote teaching and improve teachers' ability to use information technology.

3. Students should have a certain degree of technology application ability, learn to use the school's learning platform and software. Secondly, they should continue to develop the ability of independent learning and actively participate in various online and offline oral learning activities assigned by teachers. Thirdly, through group cooperative learning, they should complete learning tasks together with group members to enhance mutual assistance and communication. Fourthly, they ought to

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

correct mistakes in time according to the teacher's evaluation and feedback. In addition, students should have the belief of self-worth affirmation, and face the difficulties and challenges in learning with a positive attitude. When encountering problems in learning, they should take the initiative to seek advice from teachers and classmates or seek help by using resources such as discussion boards or forums of online learning platforms. Finally, students should look at the evaluation results objectively, analyze their strengths and weaknesses, correct mistakes in time according to the teacher's evaluation and feedback, and then make improvement plans based on them.

4. Teachers should have certain information teaching ability and are able to carry out teaching design for the combination of online and offline. Teachers should give full play to the advantages of the combination of online and offline teaching methods, provide online learning resources, assign homework, conduct tests, and conduct face-to-face communication and interaction offline to help students solve problems encountered in learning while upholding time allotment. Through the design of interesting learning activities, the use of multimedia resources and other ways to guide students to actively participate in class discussions and to improve students' learning interest and enthusiasm, will be effectively implemented.

5. Parents should provide a suitable learning environment and necessary learning tools and resources for their children, guide them in the proper use of online learning tools, and urge them to develop good study habits. Likewise, they should keep in touch with the teacher to see how their children are learning at school and how they are participating in blended learning. Furthermore, parents can participate in activities such as parent meetings and parent lectures organized by the school to communicate and share experience with other parents, and jointly discuss the implementation effect and improvement direction of blended teaching.

6. Future researchers, may use this study as a reference for future research.

References

Li, H.Y. (2021). Research on the application of Online and Offline mixed teaching mode based on "Super Star Learning Access" in Public English teaching. *English on Campus* (34), 54-55.

Zhang, C. (2023). Research on blended college English teaching model in the context of "Internet +". *Internet + Education*, 23(4).

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10730171

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.